

ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY STUDY OF DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS OF A HIGH-POWER PHOTOVOLTAIC IRRIGATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents an economic feasibility study of different configurations of a PV-grid high-power PV irrigation system in Alto Aragón, Spain. The 1574 kWp PV generator is installed in a previously only-grid pumping station with five motorpumps and, in the new configurations, PV can feed 3 of these 5 motorpumps. Conf.1 is a stand-alone solution since 3 pumps are fed by PV and the energy that is not consumed is wasted, Conf.2 is a stand-alone plus grid-connected solution in which the motorpumps are fed by PV during the irrigation period and PV energy is sold to the grid outside this period, and Conf.3 considers that PV energy can be directly used or exported throughout the year according to the pumping station needs. The PV energy consumed by the system is 1241.7 kWh/kWp, while the total energy used achieves 2016.8 kWh/kWp for Conf.3. Economic results show Profitability Index values in the 2.0-2.4 €/€ range, Internal Rate of Return values in the 5.52-7.23 % range, and Payback Period values in the 12-15 years range. The Levelized Cost of Electricity are in the 4.82-6.40 c€/kWh range, which means that savings can achieve up to 53% when compared to the only-grid system.

Keywords: Economic Analysis, Energy Performance, PV Pumping

1 INTRODUCTION

High-power photovoltaic irrigation systems (PVIS) are growing worldwide due to the increasing price of electricity from the electric grid and diesel generators [1], as well as the trend to phase-out fossil fuels. Currently, there is a lack of experience about this kind of high-power systems, which limits the feasibility assessment of its investment.

A 1574 kWp PVIS is currently under construction in Alto Aragón, Spain. The aim of this article is to provide the PV community an economic assessment of a high-power PVIS, evaluating the economic feasibility of partially substituting grid-powered irrigation systems with PVIS. Three different possible configurations will be studied and a discussion about the advantages and disadvantages of each one is presented.

The relevance of this paper lies on the study of the economic feasibility of a PVIS with more than 1 MWp. Up to now, this was only performed for small power systems [2-6] and for systems up to 360 kWp [7]. For this reason, there is the need to explore this solution for professional agriculture exploitations with high power systems (large irrigation communities, large farms, and agro-industries). For example, the system under analysis belongs to one of the irrigation communities of Riegos del Alto Aragón (which manages the largest irrigation system in Europe that consumes more than 50 GWh of energy per year) [8]. Accordingly, this study and this installation can be used as a reference for other similar systems.

To evaluate the economic feasibility, firstly, the energy and water productivity of the system is obtained through a simulation exercise done with SISIFO (a free software that allows the simulation of PVIS) [9].

Then, the economic analysis is performed. The economic profitability of the systems is evaluated in terms of the Net Present Cost (NPC), the Profitability Index (PI), the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and the Payback Period (PBP). The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is also calculated.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Description of the system

A pumping station made up of five motor-pumps of 450 kW, pumping water from a channel to a water pool, is located in Alto Aragón, Spain (latitude 41.85°N, longitude 0.387°W). The irrigation period (IP) runs from February to October, which means that energy is only necessary in this period, and the annual energy demand is around 3 GWh. Figure 1 shows the monthly energy consumption of the system, in which can be seen that the maximum energy demand is in August, followed by July and September.

Figure 1: Monthly energy consumption.

In the next months, this system will be fed by a 1574 kWp PV generator. A PV-only solution is not enough to feed the irrigation system because, in some months of the year, the number of irrigation hours per day is higher than the number of hours of sunshine. Accordingly, in the configurations under analysis, a hybrid PV-grid solution is needed [10] – three motorpumps can be fed by PV during the day and all the five motorpumps can be fed by the national grid during the night. Considering this constrain, three different configurations are analyzed:

- A stand-alone solution, in which the PV generator will feed three of the five pumps. The PV energy not used by the pumping

station is wasted (Conf.1, Figure 2).

- A stand-alone plus grid-connection solution in which the system will be a stand-alone configuration during the IP, and a grid-connected configuration outside the IP. This way, the PV generator can inject energy into the grid (Conf.2, Figure 3). The switch will be like in Figure 3 during the IP and will be in its other position outside the IP.
- A stand-alone plus grid-connection solution in which the PV system will be able to simultaneously feed the pumping station and export the energy surplus to the grid during the whole year (Conf.3, Figure 4);

Figure 2: Conf.1: stand-alone solution.

Figure 3: Conf.2: the PV generator fed the motorpumps during the irrigation period with the switch in the position of this figure, while outside the irrigation period the PV energy is sold to the national grid.

Figure 4: Conf.3: the energy from the PV generator can be directly used to feed the motorpumps or sold to the national grid along the year.

2.2 Energy performance

Firstly, the energy and water productivity of the system is obtained through a simulation exercise done with SISIFO (a free software that allows the simulation of PVIS) [9].

The difference between the energy obtained with PV and the real consumption of the system will be supplied by the national grid during night hours.

2.3 Economic study

For the estimations of the economic indicators, the annual cash flows were calculated for the whole lifetime of the system (25 years), considering the initial investment cost and the annual profits obtained. The initial investment cost was 0.8 €/Wp for Conf.1 and 0.9 €/Wp for Conf.2 and Conf.3 (this happens because in the last configurations a grid inverter needs to be installed). The annual profits are given by the economic savings obtained by substituting the national grid for the PV energy.

The installation of a PVIS, instead of a traditional grid-connected system, will be economically feasible when the resulting PI is bigger than 1, the IRR is higher than the discount rate, and the PBP is significantly lower than the lifetime of the system.

In this study, the irrigator community must have 20% of the investment and the remaining 80% is obtained as a loan and returned in 10 years.

The energy is sold to the national grid at 4.69 c€/kWh – the average value in Spain in the last 10 years [11].

The full methodology to calculate the economic indicators can be found at [12].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Energy productivity

Table I shows the PV energy productivity (the total energy used, the energy consumed by the pumping station, and the one exported to the national grid for the different configurations under analysis). The energy consumed by the pumping station is 1241.7 kWh/kWp for the three configurations under analysis, while the energy coming from the national grid to fulfill the remaining consumption is 673.82 kWh/kWp. In what concerns PV used, as expected, it increased from Conf.1 to Conf.3 because in the first configuration energy not used in the pumping station is wasted, in Conf.2 the energy not used in the IP can be sold to the national grid and only in Conf.3 all the PV energy potentially generated is used.

It is important to highlight that Conf.1 is a stand-alone solution and, in general, permissions and authorizations are easier to obtain. For Conf.2 and Conf.3 there is the need to require permissions and authorizations that can be denied by the energy distribution companies.

Table I: PV energy for the three configurations under analysis

	PV Energy Used [kWh/kWp]	PV Energy Consumed [kWh/kWp]	PV Energy Exported [kWh/kWp]
Conf.1	1241.70	1241.70	0.00
Conf.2	1553.57	1241.70	311.87
Conf.3	2016.78	1241.70	775.08

3.2 Economic feasibility

Figure 5 shows the *LCOE* of the previous system and of the three different configurations under analysis. As can be seen, the use of PV will decrease the *LCOE* of the system when compared to the only-grid solution. The new *LCOE* will range from 4.82 c€/kWh to 6.40 c€/kWh, which represents *LCOE* savings from around 38% to 53%. As expected, the higher the use of PV, the lower the *LCOE*.

Figure 5: *LCOE* of the previously system fed by the national grid and of the three different configurations under analysis.

Figure 6 shows the *NPC* of the different configurations under analysis. As expected, the highest the energy used the highest the *NPC*.

Figure 6: *NPC* of the three different configurations under analysis.

In terms of *PI* (Figure 7), values are in the 2.00-2.40 €/€ range, and in terms of *IRR* (Figure 8), values are in the 5.52-7.23%. The highest values are obtained for Conf.3, the one that maximizes the energy used. Results for Conf.1 and Conf.2 are similar since Conf.1 has a lower use of PV but also a lower *ICC* than Conf.2.

Figure 7: *PI* of the three different configurations under analysis.

Figure 8: *IRR* of the three different configurations under analysis.

The *PBP*s (Figure 9) are lower than the lifetime of the system: ranging from 13 years in Conf. 3 to 15 years in Conf.1 and Conf.2.

Figure 9: *PBP* of the three different configurations under analysis.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Results show the economic feasibility of partially substituting the energy source of a pumping station in Alto Aragón, Spain. Previously, the station was only fed by the national grid and this study considers the introduction of a 1574 kWp PV generator to decrease grid dependence and, as a consequence, energy costs. Three different configurations of PV systems are studied: a stand-alone configuration (Conf.1), and two stand-alone plus grid-connection solution (Conf.2 in which PV energy can be sold to the national grid outside the irrigation period, and Conf.3 in which all the PV energy not used by the PV generator can be sold to the national grid).

The *LCOE* of the only-grid system was 10.37 c€/kWh and savings up to 53% can be seen with the use of PV. For the different configurations under analysis, *LCOE* ranges from 4.82 c€/kWh to 6.40 c€/kWh, *NPC* values are all positive, *PI* values are all higher than 1 €/€, *IRR* are higher than 5% and the maximum *PBP* is 15 years.

As expected, the possibility to export PV energy to the national grid increases the economic profitability of the systems and must be considered, if possible, to increase the economic feasibility of high-power PVIS.

Authors believe that this configuration is better than the standard self-consumption solution since it allows costs reductions in terms of both energy used from the grid and contracted power, but a future research line is the comparison of the results presented in this work with the self-consumption solution.

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